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CHARACTERISTICS OF MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF THE SPLEEN IN TRAUMATIC SPINAL CORD INJURIES

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Resume: *The present article includes the results of a scientific study aimed at investigating the morphometric parameters of the spleen in 3-month-old rats with mild spinal injuries.*

Based on the obtained data, it should be noted that a comparative morphometric analysis on the 7th day after mild spinal cord contusion shows a gradual increase in white pulp atrophy and compensatory remodeling of the red pulp. This is manifested by a decrease in the proportion of white pulp on day 7 (39.3%), day 14 (35.4%), and day 21 (27.6%) compared to the control group (48.7%).

The most significant changes are observed on the 21st day, when white pulp atrophy reaches its maximum and is accompanied by pronounced collagenization of the red pulp.

Keywords: *spleen, lymphoid follicles, red and white pulp, trabecular artery.*

Резюме: *Настоящая статья включает результаты научного исследования, цель которых изучить морфометрические параметры селезенки 3-х месячных крыс при спинномозговых травмах легкой степени.*

Основываясь на полученные данные, следует отметить, что сравнительный анализ морфометрии на 7 сутки после ушиба спинного мозга лёгкой степени показывает поэтапное увеличение атрофии белой пульпы и компенсаторной перестройки красной пульпы. Это проявляется уменьшением белой пульпы на 7 день (39,3) на 14 сутки (35,4) и 21 сутки 27,6% по сравнению контрольной группы (48,7%).

Наиболее значимые изменения приходятся на 21-е сутки, когда атрофия белой пульпы достигает максимума и сочетается с выраженной коллагенизацией красной пульпы.

Ключевые слова: *селезенка, лимфоидные фолликулы, красная и белая пульпа, трабекулярная артерия.*

Резюме: *Ушибу мақолада энгил даражадаги орқа мия шикастланишида 3 ойлик калмушлар талогининг морфометрик курсаткичларини урганишига қаратилган илмий тадқиқот натижалари келтирилган.*

Олинган маълумотларга асосланиб айтиши мумкинки, орқа мия энгил даражада лат ейганидан сўнг 7 суткада ўтказилган морфометрия таҳлили оқ пулпаннинг босқичма-босқич атрофияси ва қизил пулпаннинг компенсацион қайта тузилишини кўрсатади. Бу ҳолат оқ пулпаннинг 7 кунда 39.3 %, 14 кунда 35.4 % ва 21 кунда 27.6 % гача камайиши билан ифодаланади, бу эса назорат гуруҳига (48.7 %) нисбатан сезиларли фарқни ташиқил этади.

Энг муҳим ўзгаришлар 21 суткада кузатилади — бу вақтда оқ пулпаннинг атрофияси энг юқори даражага этади ва қизил пулпаннинг кучли коллагенланиши билан бирга кечади.

Калит сўзлар: *Талок, лимфоид фолликулалар, кизил ва оқ пульпа, трабекуляр артерия.*

In modern medicine, special attention is paid to studying the effects of adverse environmental factors. The human body cannot be considered without the influence of natural conditions and human activity. Throughout evolutionary development, the environment influences all living organisms. The function of adaptive immunity, which ensures cellular and humoral homeostasis, is

performed by the organs of the immune system, the morphological basis of which is lymphoid tissue. Its largest representative is the spleen [3].

The spleen is one of the most complex peripheral organs of the immune system. Discrepancies in data on its structure stem from the fact that most studies are conducted on laboratory animals, and the results are

extrapolated to humans. The few studies based on histological material from the human spleen do not allow for a comprehensive assessment of the morphometry of pulp compartments and the characteristics of its cellular composition [4,9,10, 11,12,13].

Spinal cord injury disrupts central regulation, leading to dysfunction of organs and systems below the level of injury, including impaired control of peripheral immune organs, especially the spleen [5,8]. The severity of the consequences of spinal cord injury is determined by the level and nature of the damage, metabolic and regenerative characteristics, lifestyle, and time since the injury. The injury triggers a cascade of inflammatory reactions, cell death, and restructuring of the functions of the nervous and immune systems with the release of regulatory peptides and proinflammatory cytokines [6,11].

The cellular inflammatory response of the spleen in spinal cord injury has not been adequately studied. An increase in monocyte and neutrophil counts with a slight decrease in T- and B-lymphocytes has been observed [7]. Spinal cord injuries cause changes in organs, including the spleen, ranging from microcirculation disturbances to parenchymal atrophy, necessitating a study of their dynamics. Despite the interest in the topic, the morphology of the spleen following such injuries remains poorly understood, although its structure in humans and animals is similar [1].

Objective: to study morphological changes in the spleen tissue of 3-month-old white outbred rats in the early period (from 3 days to 4 weeks) after mild spinal cord injury at the level of the T4–T12 vertebrae in the intervals of 7–14–21 days.

To achieve the goal and solve the set tasks, we conducted a study on 45 mature outbred white rats.

Material and methods. In order to accurately identify morphological and morphometric parameters of the spleen structure with varying degrees of severity of spinal cord injury, the following five groups were formed:

I - animals, control group 3-5 months old

II - experimental group 3 months old that received a spinal cord injury for 3 days

III - experimental group 3 months old that received a spinal cord injury for 7 days

IV - experimental group 3 months old that received a spinal cord injury for 14 days

The experimental animals were kept under standard conditions. Both experimental and control groups were fed the same diet. Rats were sacrificed at 3-5 months of postnatal development under ether anesthesia. After opening the abdominal cavity, the spleen was removed. Its absolute weight was determined using a ruler and calipers, as well as its length, width, and thickness (the latter two were measured at the hilum).

Subsequently, the spleen and its parts were fixed in 10% neutralized formalin for 10 days, washed with running water for 3-4 hours and dehydrated in increasing concentrations of alcohol and chloroform; paraffin blocks were prepared using generally accepted methods. Paraffin sections 5-7 mkm thick were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The spleen structures in the preparations were examined morphometrically using an ocular micrometer. The total thickness of the spleen capsule and the thickness of collagen fiber bundles were measured.

In the spleen parenchyma, the ratio of red pulp to white pulp was determined, as well as the number of primary and secondary lymphoid nodules and their germinal centers, the width of the marginal, paracortical and edge zone of lymphatic nodules, the relative area of connective tissue elements and white pulp (relative to the total area of the section).

To study the cytoarchitecture of splenic lymphoid structures, cell counts were performed under oil immersion at 10x100 magnification using a NOVEL Model NLCD-307 microscope (China). The nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio of epithelial cells in the spleen was calculated using a grid of 100 nodal points mounted in the eyepiece. Using a morphometric grid, the number of cells placed on the microscope eyepiece was counted. The total number of lymphocytes in

lymph nodes lacking a germinal center and periarterial lymphatic cuffs was determined per unit cross-sectional area.

The histological and cytomorphometric data obtained during the study were processed using mathematical methods, which were carried out directly from the general matrix of the Microsoft

Office data package “Excel 7.0” on a Pentium-IV personal computer.

Results of our own research.

In the control group (Fig. 1), the classic spleen architecture is striking: the white and red pulp occupy almost equal areas (48.7% and 51.3%), which is confirmed by morphometry (white pulp area: 1.39×10^6 px², red pulp area: 1.46×10^6 px²).

Fig. 1. Microscopic image of the spleen of 3-month-old rats of the control group. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. UV 20x10. 1 - Red pulp; 2 - white pulp; 3 - PALM; 4 - trabecular artery.

The lymphoid follicles are clearly structured, their germinal centers are rich in B-lymphocytes (198 cells), the PALMs are densely populated with T-lymphocytes (242 cells), and the blast elements (32 cells, approximately 6–7%) are harmoniously integrated. The visual impression is normal, with no hint of pathological changes.

As early as the 7th day after spinal cord contusion (Fig. 2), a thinning of the white pulp becomes noticeable: follicles lose

definition, and the PALMs narrow. Morphometry confirms: the area of the white pulp decreases to 39.3% (1.12×10^6 px²), while the red pulp increases to 60.7%.

The T-lymphocyte count drops to 184 (-22% relative to control), B-lymphocytes to 137 (-18%), and blast cells increase to 46 (a 35% increase). Under immersion, dissonance is striking: mature cells disappear, and yellow clumps of blasts become dominant.

Fig. 2. Microscopic image of the spleen of 3-month-old rats of the experimental group in the early period (7 days) after mild spinal cord contusion. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. UV 20x10. 1 - Decreased volume of white pulp (due to a decrease in mature lymphocytes); 2- Decrease in the mantle and marginal zones; 3-Red pulp. Moderate congestion of the venous sinuses, foci of hemolysis. The number of macrophages is slightly increased; 4-decrease in the volume of PALM (due to a decrease in the number of T-lymphocytes); 5-perivascular sclerosis of the trabecular artery.

Foci of hemolysis appear in the red pulp, and the venous sinuses become moderately engorged. The final impression is one of initial atrophy with a compensatory shift toward immature cells.

On the 14th day (Fig. 3.1.3, 3.1.3A), the changes become more pronounced. The white pulp is reduced to 35.4% (0.97×10^6 px²), its architecture appears "torn": the mantle and marginal zones are erased. The number of T-lymphocytes decreases to 126 (–

48%), B-lymphocytes to 92 (–53%), with blast cells reaching 41 cells (≈17%).

The morphological picture creates the impression of depleted lymphoid tissue, where mature cells give way to foci of blastic proliferative cells. The red pulp becomes increasingly plethoracent, and hemolysis in the perisinusoidal areas is more pronounced. The functional dependence is obvious: atrophy of the white pulp leads to a decrease in the immune response, while the red pulp is activated compensatorily.

Fig. 3. Microscopic image of the spleen of 3-month-old rats of the experimental group in the early period (14 days) after mild spinal cord contusion. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. UV 20x10. 1-Red pulp, increased hemolysis in the perisinusoidal region. 2- Reduction in the volume of white pulp (due to a decrease in the number of mature lymphocytes); 3- Reduction in the volume of the mantle and marginal zones.

By the 21st day (Fig. 3), a stable chronic restructuring has developed. The white pulp is reduced to 27.6% (0.72×10^6 px²), PALM are represented by single islands of T-lymphocytes (84 cells, –65%), and only 67 B-lymphocytes remain (–66%). Germinal centers contain predominantly blast cells (38, ≈23%), creating a picture of "pseudocompensation." However, van

Gieson staining reveals a more serious process: collagenization of the red pulp. Collagen fibers intensively envelop the perivascular zones and intersinusoidal septa, thickening the vascular walls.

However, van Gieson staining reveals a more serious process: collagenization of the red pulp. Collagen fibers intensively envelop the perivascular zones and intersinusoidal

septa, thickening the vascular walls. Morphometry records an increase in the red pulp area to 72.4% ($1.89 \times 10^6 \text{ px}^2$), and the relative collagen volume almost doubles compared to day 14 ($p < 0.05$). The final

impression is that the spleen enters a phase of fibrous remodeling, when atrophy of the white pulp is combined with collagenization of the red pulp stroma.

Fig. 4. Microscopic image of the spleen of 3-month-old rats of the experimental group in the early period (21 days) after spinal cord contusion. Van Gieson staining. UV 20x10. 1- Collagenization of the trabeculae of the red pulp; 2-white pulp (enlargement of the germinal center due to an increase in blast lymphocytes); 3-decrease in PALM; 4-thickening of the PALM arterial wall.

Table 1

Morphometric parameters of the spleen of 3-month-old white outbred rats in the early period after mild spinal cord injury (M±m)

Indicator	Control	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21
White pulp area, $\times 10^6 \text{ px}^2$ (%)	1,39 ± 0,05 (48,7%)	1,12 ± 0,04 (39,3%)	0,97 ± 0,03 (35,4%)	0,72 ± 0,03 (27,6%)
Red pulp area, $\times 10^6 \text{ px}^2$ (%)	1,46 ± 0,06 (51,3%)	1,73 ± 0,05 (60,7%)	1,77 ± 0,04 (64,6%)	1,89 ± 0,05 (72,4%)
T-lymphocytes, cell count	242 ± 8	184 ± 6* (-22%)	126 ± 5** (-48%)	84 ± 4** (-65%)
B-lymphocytes, cell count	198 ± 7	137 ± 6* (-18%)	92 ± 4** (-53%)	67 ± 3** (-66%)
Blast lymphocytes, cell count	32 ± 2 (6-7%)	46 ± 3* (≈2%)	41 ± 2* (17%)	38 ± 2* (23%)
Collagenized stroma in red pulp, %	8,2 ± 0,5	12,7 ± 0,6	18,9 ± 0,8*	31,5 ± 1,1**

Notes: - * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$ compared to control. Values in parentheses are relative changes or percentage of the total cell count.

Conclusion.

Thus, on the seventh day of postnatal development in rats, a decrease in T-lymphocytes (-22%) and B-lymphocytes (-

18%) is observed, along with an increase in blast cells (12%). Morphologically, this is manifested by a rarefaction of follicles and a decrease in PALM. By day 21, the maximum

pathological changes are reached: white pulp is reduced to 27.6% (-43%), and T- and B-lymphocyte counts decrease by 65–66% compared to controls. Comparative analysis of morphometric data on days 7, 14, and 21 after mild spinal cord contusion reveals a gradual increase in white pulp atrophy and compensatory remodeling of the red pulp.

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THE EFFECTS OF VARIOUS EXOGENOUS HARMFUL FACTORS ON THE MALE REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *The male reproductive system is highly sensitive to a wide range of exogenous harmful factors, including environmental toxins, radiation, heat, lifestyle-related exposures, pharmaceuticals, and industrial chemicals. These factors can significantly impair*